

THE ESSENCE AND CONTENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract: The word "business" is an English word, and it is an entrepreneurial activity, or in other words, an activity aimed at making people profit. Business covers the relations between all participants of the market economy and includes not only the actions of businessmen, but also consumers, hired workers, and employees of the state system. In this case, they are synonyms of the word business, and in a certain sense, such concepts as commerce and trade are considered. In general, business is the work and activity of a person in the system of market relations.

Keywords: business, market relations, local economy.

It is necessary to connect the definition of small business with its content. As mentioned above, the nature of small business is compatible with entrepreneurship. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity" adopted on May 25, 2000, entrepreneurship is an initiative activity aimed at obtaining income (profit) carried out by subjects of entrepreneurial activity in accordance with legal documents, taking risks and under their own property responsibility. A small business entity never aims to remain at the same level of activity, but rather seeks to develop and expand its activities.

Although it is stated in scientific sources that entrepreneurship is developed and scientifically based, first of all, in the West, this activity was appreciated much earlier as the economic values of the peoples of the East. Let's say that commodity-money relations first developed in the East and gradually moved to the West. Our study, approached from the point of view of the topic being studied and researched, also shows that even in today's 3000-year-old "Avesta" it is repeatedly emphasized

that not only doing business, but also achieving the desired goal with the results of the activity. In this, it is emphasized that "it is necessary to plow the land not once, but a hundred times in order to use the land, plant wheat and achieve the results."

A number of features of our national entrepreneurship are also expressed in the work of the great scientist Farabi "The City of Virtuous People". In this work, he calls people to become owners, that is, entrepreneurs, and as a result, people do not live in poverty, and to follow the rules and regulations in spending both for production needs and for personal consumption. Farabi explains that possessing property is not a bad habit, as opposed to hoarding it for nothing, because wealth is better than living in poverty if it is accumulated honestly. He states that "If someone accumulates the property for himself without putting it into circulation for profit, he will cause great harm. "Temur's Laws" is of particular importance in studying the theoretical foundations of entrepreneurship from the features of Eastern mentality. The reason for all the universal victories of Amir Temur is that he works with entrepreneurship, he made entrepreneurship the motto of his thinking and action. In his time, Amir Temur was able to see not only the characteristics of entrepreneurship, but also the principles of its implementation and defined them as:

- it is necessary to provide assistance from the state treasury to entrepreneurs who have lost their investment for certain reasons, so that they can restore their previous potential;
- caring for intelligent people engaged in entrepreneurship and handicrafts, appreciating their services and thus encouraging them to be creative and meritorious;
- fair distribution of income subject to rules such as purity, faith and justice;
- believed that it is enough to invest in people who are engaged in business activities.

Abdulla Avloni, an ardent patriot and enlightener, thought in the description of entrepreneurship: "A person observes until it becomes clear to him which of his actions are useful and which are harmful, and he selects and adopts the useful ones, and rejects the harmful ones and avoids them." Today, this idea is a certain

foundation stone for following the rule of economic choice with entrepreneurship, choosing activities by spending on what it is economically desirable to produce them in the conditions of limited resources.

In fact, entrepreneurship is primarily an intellectual activity of an active and enterprising person who uses more or less wealth in his hands to engage in business. That's why "entrepreneurship" means not only earning money, but earning income through creative activity.

The famous economist Joseph Schumpeter (1883-1950) in his book "Theory of Economic Development" described an entrepreneur as an innovator, that is, a person who creates new things. "The task of an entrepreneur is to reform (update) the production method by implementing new discoveries. In a broad sense, the task of an entrepreneur is to use new technologies to produce new goods or modernize old ones based on a newly opened market or raw material base.

At the core of entrepreneurship is an independent initiative based on the idea of entrepreneurship, focused on profit, goal-oriented, responsibility-based activity. There is no generally recognized definition of entrepreneurship either abroad or in our country. American scientist R. Khizrich states that "Entrepreneurship is the process of creating something new that has its own value, and an entrepreneur is a person who spends all the necessary time and day for this, takes all the financial, psychological and social risks, and is satisfied with money and achievements as a reward." English professor A. Hoskin explains that "a person who conducts work at his own expense, is personally involved in business management, has personal responsibility for providing the necessary tools, and makes independent decisions, is an individual entrepreneur."

Based on the above considerations, small business can be characterized as a form of entrepreneurial activity, the level of production scale of which combines the main elements of entrepreneurship, such as risk-taking, initiative, innovation, organization, striving for maximum profit with minimal expenses, the criteria of which are determined by legislation. This level of scale is the main factor in

determining its criteria. The main reason for different definitions of the concept of "small business" is that these criteria are different.

Criteria for representing a small business. The criteria representing a small business can be divided into two large groups:

1. Quantitative or numerical approach to small business activity and organizational status. They include the number of employees, the value of the authorized capital, the value of assets, the volume of production, the volume of realization of products and services, etc.

2. By quality indicators or quality approach. These criteria include the monopolistic nature of the activity, the form of ownership, differences in the organization of economic activity within the network, and the interaction between small and large production.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Promotion of the Development of Small and Private Entrepreneurship", the main subjects of small and private entrepreneurship include enterprises engaged in entrepreneurial activities and the number of employees during the reporting period does not exceed the following levels:

up to 50 people - small enterprises in the field of industry and construction;

up to 10 people - in science and science service industries;

up to 25 people - in agriculture and other industries;

Up to 5 people - in retail production.

In international practice, the following (criterion) indicators are often used to determine the scale of small business entities:

number of employees;

applicability to economic sectors;

size of charter fund;

ownership;

total assets;

turnover, etc.

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